

GRAPH THEORY- FUZZY GRAPH COLORING AND ITS APPLICATION

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Abstract : Coloring of fuzzy graphs has several real life applications in combinatorial optimization issues like traffic light system, examination programming, register allocation, etc. In this paper, we analyze the vertex and edge coloring on bipartite graphs using the concept of as fuzzy numbers through the α -cuts of the fuzzy graphs which are crisp graphs. For different values of α -cuts which depend on edge and vertex membership value of the graph, we will get different graph and different chromatic number. The method for locating fuzzy chromatic set is recommended and verified.

Key words: Fuzzy graphs, Fuzzy chromatic number

INTRODUCTION

Graph theory, branch of mathematics concerned with network of points connected by links. The origin of Graph theory started with the problem oh Königsberg bridge in 1735. The Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler solved this Königsberg problem. The Königsberg bridge problem was an old puzzle concerning the possibility of finding a path over every one of the seven bridge that span a forked river flowing past an island but without crossing any bridge twice. In graph theory, Graph coloring is a special case of graph labelling of colours to components of graphs. The first result about graph coloring deals almost with the planar graph in the form of coloring of maps. While trying to color the map of the countries of England, Francis Guthrie, postulated the four color conjecture, noting that four colors were sufficient to color the map so that no regions sharing common border receiving same color. In 1879, Alfred Kempe published a paper that claimed to establish the result. In 1890 Heawood said that every planar map can be colored with no more than five colors, using the idea of Kempe. Finally the four color problem was proved in 1976 by Kenneth Appel and Wolfgang Haken.

In 1912, George David Birkhoff introduced chromatic polynomial to study coloring problems which was generalised to Tutte polynomial by Tutte, important structure in algebraic graph theory. Graph coloring has been studied as an algorithmic problem since in the early 1970's. In 1965, Zadeh introduced the notion of fuzzy set which is characterised by a membership function which assigns to each object a grade of membership which ranges from 0 to 1. The first definition of fuzzy graph was introduced by Kaufmann (1973), based on Zadeh's fuzzy relation (1971). Fuzzy graph was first introduced by Rosenfeld and further discussed and developed by many others. Fuzzy graph coloring is one in every of the foremost vital problems of fuzzy graph theory, it is mainly studied in combinatorial optimization like traffic light control, exam scheduling, register allocation etc.

As an advancement fuzzy coloring of a fuzzy graph was outlined by authors Eslahchi and Onagh in 2004, and later developed by them a fuzzy vertex coloring in 2006. This fuzzy vertex coloring was extended to fuzzy total coloring in terms of family of fuzzy set by S.Lavanya and R.Sattanathan. The concept of chromatic number of fuzzy graphs was introduced by Munoz.S. Eslahchi and Onagh defined fuzzy coloring of fuzzy graphs and defined fuzzy chromatic number $\chi^f(G)$. Anjaly and Sunitha introduced chromatic number $\chi(G)$ of fuzzy graphs G incorporating the features of definition given in Munoz and Eslahchi[8] and established that $\chi(G) = \chi^f(G)$.

2.PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1:

A **fuzzy graph** is an ordered triple $G: (V, \sigma, \mu)$ where V is a set of vertices $\{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$, σ is the fuzzy set of V (i e) $\sigma: V \rightarrow [0,1]$ and is denoted by $\sigma = \{(u_1, \sigma(u_1)), (u_2, \sigma(u_2)), \dots, (u_n, \sigma(u_n))\}$ and μ is a fuzzy relation on σ (ie) $\mu(u, v) \leq \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v)$.

Fig 1. A Fuzzy graph

Definition 2.2 :

We denote the underlying **crisp graph** of G by $G^*: (\sigma^*, \mu^*)$ where $\sigma^* = \{u \in V : \sigma(u) > 0\}$ and $\mu^* = \{(u, v) \in V \times V : \mu(u, v) > 0\}$.

Definition 2.3:

The α – **cut set of fuzzy set** A is defined as A_α is made up of member whose membership is not less than α . $A_\alpha = \{x \in X / \mu_A(x) \geq \alpha\}$. α - cut set of fuzzy set is a crisp set.

Definition 2.4:

The α – **cut set of fuzzy graph** defined as $G_\alpha = (V_\alpha, E_\alpha)$ where $V_\alpha = \{v \in V: \sigma \geq \alpha\}$ and $E_\alpha = \{e \in E: \mu \geq \alpha\}$.

Definition 2.5:

Two vertices u and v in G are called **adjacent** if $\frac{1}{2}[\sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v)] \leq \mu(u, v)$.

Definition 2.6:

The **degree of vertex** v in G denoted by $deg_G(v)$ is the number of adjacent vertices to V and maximum degree of G is defined by $\Delta(G) = \max\{deg_G(v): v \in V\}$ and the minimum degree is $\delta(G) = \min\{deg_G(v): v \in V\}$.

Definition 2.7:

A fuzzy graph is said to be **complete** if $\mu(u, v) = \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v) \forall u, v \in V$.

fig 2. complete fuzzy graph

Definition 2.8:

Given a graph $G: (V, E)$, a **coloring function** is a mapping $C: V \rightarrow N$ identifying $C(i)$ as the color of a node $i \in V$, in such a way that two adjacent nodes cannot share the same color, $C(i) \neq C(j)$ if $\{i, j\} \in E$.

Definition 2.9:

For a fuzzy graph $\hat{G} = (V, \mu)$, its **vertex chromatic number** is the fuzzy number $\chi(G) = \{(x, v(x)) : x \in X\}$ where $X = \{1, 2, \dots, |V|\}$, $v(x) = \sup\{\alpha \in I : x \in A_\alpha\}$, $x \in X$, $A_\alpha = \{1, 2, \dots, \chi_\alpha\}$, $\alpha \in I$.

Definition 2.10:

For a fuzzy graph $\hat{G} = (V, \mu)$, its **edge chromatic number** is the fuzzy number $\chi'_f(\hat{G}) = \{(x, \lambda(x)) : x \in X\}$ where $X = \{1, 2, \dots, \Delta + 1\}$, $\lambda(x) = \sup\{\alpha \in I : x \in A_\alpha\}$, $A_\alpha = \{1, 2, \dots, \chi'_\alpha\}$, $\alpha \in I$.

Definition 2.11:

For a fuzzy graph $\hat{G} = (V, \mu)$, its **total chromatic number** is the fuzzy number $\chi_f^T(\hat{G}) = \{(x, \tau(x)) : x \in X\}$ where $X = \{1, 2, \dots, \Delta + 2\}$, $\tau(x) = \sup\{\alpha \in I : x \in A_\alpha\}$, $A_\alpha = \{1, 2, \dots, \chi_f^T\}$, $\alpha \in I$.

3. Fuzzy Coloring Using $\alpha - Cuts$:

Using $\alpha - cuts$ of the complete bipartite fuzzy graph we have colored the vertex, edge and both vertex and edges of fuzzy graph.

3.1 Vertex coloring of fuzzy graph using $\alpha - cuts$:

Let we take a fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ where V has six vertices and membership values of those vertices are $\sigma = \{0.8, 1, 0.8, 0.7, 0.9, 0.7\}$ and graph G has 9 edges and membership values of these edges are in μ .

		v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6			v_1	v_2	v_3	v_4	v_5	v_6
$\mu =$	v_1	0	0	0	e_9	e_5	e_1	$\mu =$	v_1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.5	0.5
	v_2	0	0	0	e_8	e_4	e_2		v_2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.7	0.7
	v_3	0	0	0	e_7	e_6	e_3		v_3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.8	0.6
	v_4	e_9	e_8	e_7	0	0	0		v_4	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0
	v_5	e_5	e_4	e_6	0	0	0		v_5	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0
	v_6	e_1	e_2	e_3	0	0	0		v_6	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0

Adjacent matrix I

Adjacent matrix II

Here the adjacent matrix I represent the name of edges between the vertices and adjacent matrix II represents the membership values of the edges. Example : edge between the vertices v_1 and v_4 is e_9 and membership value of that edge is 0.8.

Let fuzzy graph $G = (V_F, E_F)$ be a fuzzy graph where

$$V_1 = \{(v_1, 0.8), (v_2, 1), (v_3, 0.8), (v_4, 0.7), (v_5, 0.9), (v_6, 0.7)\}$$

$$E_F = \{(e_1, 0.5), (e_2, 0.7), (e_3, 0.6), (e_4, 0.7), (e_5, 0.5), (e_6, 0.8), (e_7, 0.7), (e_8, 0.6), (e_9, 0.8)\}$$

In the above defined fuzzy graph, there are six $\alpha - cuts$ are presented. They are $\{0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1\}$. For every value of α , we can find the graph G_α and its fuzzy chromatic number.

For $\alpha = 0.5$, fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ and where $\sigma = \{0.8, 1, 0.8, 0.7, 0.9, 0.7\}$ and

$$\mu = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_4 & v_5 & v_6 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_4 \\ v_5 \\ v_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.8 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.6 & 0.7 & 0.7 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.8 & 0.6 \\ 0.8 & 0.6 & 0.7 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.5 & 0.7 & 0.8 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.5 & 0.7 & 0.6 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

For $\alpha = 0.5, G_{0.5} = (V_{0.5}, E_{0.5})$ where $V_{0.5}$ and $E_{0.5}$ both are crisp set. $V_{0.5}$ is the collection of those elements of fuzzy set V_F whose membership value is greater than or equal to 0.5. So $V_{0.5} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ and same as $E_{0.5}$ is a collection of those elements of fuzzy set E_F whose membership values are greater than or equal to 0.5.

So $E_{0.5} = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5, e_6, e_7, e_8, e_9\}$. Here we need minimum 6 colors to proper color all the vertices of the graph $G_{0.5}$, so the chromatic number of $G_{0.5}$ is 6.

For $\alpha = 0.5, \chi_{0.5} = \chi(G_{0.5}) = 6$.

For $\alpha = 0.6$, fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ and where $\sigma = \{0.8, 1, 0.8, 0.7, 0.9, 0.7\}$ and

$$\mu = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_4 & v_5 & v_6 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_4 \\ v_5 \\ v_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.8 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.6 & 0.7 & 0.7 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.8 & 0.6 \\ 0.8 & 0.6 & 0.7 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.8 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.6 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

We find the graph $G_{0.6} = (V_{0.6}, E_{0.6})$ where $V_{0.5} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ and $E_{0.6} = \{e_2, e_3, e_4, e_6, e_7, e_8, e_9\}$. Here we need minimum 3 colors to proper color all the vertices of the graph $G_{0.6}$, so the chromatic number of graph $G_{0.6}$ is 3.

For $\alpha = 0.6, \chi_{0.6} = \chi(G_{0.6}) = 3$.

For $\alpha = 0.7$, fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ and where $\sigma = \{0.8, 1, 0.8, 0.7, 0.9, 0.7\}$ and

$$\mu = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_4 & v_5 & v_6 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_4 \\ v_5 \\ v_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.8 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.7 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.8 & 0.0 \\ 0.8 & 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.8 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.7 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

We find the graph $G_{0.7} = (V_{0.7}, E_{0.7})$ where $V_{0.7} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5, v_6\}$ and $E_{0.6} = \{e_2, e_3, e_4, e_6, e_7, e_8, e_9\}$. Here we need minimum 3 colors to proper color all the vertices of the graph $G_{0.7}$, so the chromatic number of $G_{0.7}$ is 3.

For $\alpha = 0.7$, $\chi_{0.7} = \chi(G_{0.7}) = 3$.

For $\alpha = 0.8$, fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ and where $\sigma = \{0.8, 1, 0.8, 0.9\}$ and

$$\mu = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_5 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_5 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.8 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.8 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

We find the graph $G_{0.8} = (V_{0.8}, E_{0.8})$ where $V_{0.8} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5\}$ and $E_{0.8} = \{e_6\}$. Here we need minimum 2 colors to proper color all the vertices of the graph $G_{0.8}$, so the chromatic number of the graph $G_{0.8}$ is 2. For $\alpha = 0.8$, $\chi_{0.8} = \chi(G_{0.8}) = 2$.

For $\alpha = 0.9$, fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ and where $\sigma = \{1, 0.9\}$ and

$$\mu = \begin{matrix} v_2 & v_5 \\ v_2 & \begin{bmatrix} 0.0 & 0.0 \\ 0.0 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \\ v_5 & \end{matrix}$$

We find the graph $G_{0.9} = (V_{0.9}, E_{0.9})$ where $V_{0.9} = \{v_2, v_5\}$ and $E_{0.9} = \{\}$. Here we need minimum 1 colors to proper color all the vertices of the graph $G_{0.9}$, so the chromatic number of the graph $G_{0.9}$ is 1. For $\alpha = 0.9$, $\chi_{0.9} = \chi(G_{0.9}) = 1$.

For $\alpha = 1$, fuzzy graph $G = (V, \sigma, \mu)$ and where $\sigma = \{1\}$ and we find the graph $G_1 = (V_1, E_1)$ where $V_1 = \{v_2\}$ and $E_1 = \{\}$. Here we need minimum 1 colors to proper color all the vertices of the graph G_1 , so the chromatic number of the graph G_1 is 1. For $\alpha = 1$, $\chi_1 = \chi(G_1) = 1$.

In the above example, six crisp graphs $G_\alpha = (V_\alpha, E_\alpha)$ are obtained by considering values of α . Now the chromatic number χ_α for any α , it can be shown that the chromatic number of fuzzy graph G is $\chi(G) = \{(6,0.5), (3,0.6), (3,0.7), (2,0.8), (1,0.9), (1,1)\}$.

3.2 Edge coloring of fuzzy graphs using $\alpha - cuts$:

Let $G_\alpha = \{(V, E_\alpha) : \alpha \in I$ be the family of $\alpha - cuts$ of $\hat{G}$, where the $\alpha - cuts$ of a fuzzy graph is a crisp graph $G_\alpha = (V, E_\alpha)$ with $E_\alpha = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, \mu_{ij} \geq \alpha\}$. In a crisp case the edge chromatic number of the graph is either Δ or $\Delta + 1$ where Δ is the maximum degree. For each $\alpha \in I$, the following Table 3.1 contains edge set E_α , the edge chromatic number χ'_f . Six crisp graphs $G_\alpha = (V, E_\alpha)$ corresponding to each α is given below.

Table 3.1

α	E_α	χ	$c_\alpha(14)$	$c_\alpha(15)$	$c_\alpha(16)$	$c_\alpha(24)$	$c_\alpha(25)$	$c_\alpha(26)$	$c_\alpha(34)$	$c_\alpha(35)$	$c_\alpha(36)$
0.4	14,15,16,24, 25,26,34,35, 36	3	2	3	1	3	1	2	1	2	3
0.5	14,15,24,25, 26,34,35,36	3	2	3	0	3	1	2	1	2	3
0.6	14,24,25,26, 34,35,36	3	2	0	0	3	1	2	1	2	3
0.7	14,25,34,35	2	2	0	0	0	1	2	1	2	0
0.8	35	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
0.9	ϕ	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

*(blue-1 , red-2 , violet-3)

$\alpha = 0.4 \quad \chi'_f = 3$

$\alpha = 0.5 \quad \chi'_f = 3$

$\alpha = 0.6 \quad \chi'_f = 3$

$\alpha = 0.7 \quad \chi'_f = 2$

$\alpha = 0.8 \quad \chi'_f = 1$

$$\alpha = 0.9 \quad \chi'_f = 0$$

Since $\Delta = 3$, for the given graph, then the fuzzy edge chromatic number of $\hat{G}$ is $\chi'_f = \{(1,0.8)(2,0.7)(3,,0.4)\}$. Hence the chromatic number is $\chi'_f = 3$.

3.3 : Fuzzy total coloring using $\alpha - cuts$:

Let $G_\alpha = \{(V, E_\alpha) : \alpha \in I$ be the family of $\alpha - cuts$ of $\hat{G}$, where the $\alpha - cuts$ of a fuzzy graph is a crisp graph $G_\alpha = (V, E_\alpha)$ with $E_\alpha = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, \mu_{ij} \geq \alpha\}$.

In a crisp case the total chromatic number of the graph is atmost $\Delta + 2$ where Δ is the maximum degree. Consider for each $\alpha \in I$, the following Table 3.2 contains the mapping $c_\alpha: (V \cup E) \rightarrow \{1,2, \dots, k\}$ and the total chromatic number χ_f^T . Six crisp graphs $G_\alpha = (V, E_\alpha)$ corresponding to each α is given below.

Table 3.2

α	χ_f^T	c_α (1)	c_α (2)	c_α (3)	c_α (4)	c_α (5)	c_α (6)	c_α (14)	c_α (15)	c_α (16)	c_α (24)	c_α (25)	c_α (26)	c_α (34)	c_α (35)	c_α (36)
0.4	5	2	2	5	3	4	4	4	5	1	5	1	3	1	3	2
0.5	5	2	2	5	3	4	4	4	5	0	5	1	3	1	3	2
0.6	5	2	2	5	3	4	4	4	0	0	5	1	3	1	3	2
0.7	4	2	2	2	3	4	4	4	0	0	0	1	3	1	3	0
0.8	3	3	1	3	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
0.9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

*(green-1 , blue-2 , violet-3 , red-4 , brown-5)

$\alpha = 0.4 \quad \chi_f^T = 5$

$\alpha = 0.5 \quad \chi_f^T = 5$

$\alpha = 0.6 \quad \chi_f^T = 5$

$$\alpha = 0.7 \quad \chi_f^T = 4$$

$$\alpha = 0.8 \quad \chi_f^T = 3$$

$$\alpha = 0.9 \quad \chi_f^T = 1$$

Since $\Delta=3$, the chromatic number is $\chi_f^T = 5$. And the total chromatic number is $\chi_f^T = \{(1,0.9), (2,,0), (3,0.8), (4,0.7), (5,0.4)\}$.

4. APPLICATIONS OF FUZZY COLORING

4.1 The traffic lights problem: The control policy of the traffic light depends mainly on the number of vehicles in the intersection line. If the traffic flow in the intersection line is high then there is a possibility of accident. When the number of vehicles in the intersection line is low then there may be less possibility of accident. The concept of accident and number of vehicles in each line could be fuzzy and it could be graduated. This graduation, which does not need to be numerical, is associated to the desired security level for the traffic. Here we represent each traffic flow with a fuzzy edge whose membership value depends on the number of the vehicles in that path. Two fuzzy vertices are adjacent if the corresponding traffic flows cross each other then there is a possibility of accident. Possibility of accident value will depend on vertex membership value. The maximum security level is attained when all lanes are considered to be in intersection with each other and the number of vehicles in each line is also high. So graph will be a complete graph. In this case, the chromatic number is the number of lanes and the control policy of the lights assure that only one movement is allowed in any slot of the cycle. On the other hand, the minimum security level is attained when the intersection edge set is empty; in this case, the chromatic number is 1 and all movements are allowed at any instant. Since the four right turns do not interfere with the other traffic flows, they can safely be dropped from our discussion. Membership values can be represented by symbolic name H for high, M for medium for low respectively.

4.2 Scheduling: Vertex coloring models to a number of scheduling problems. In the cleanest form, a given set of jobs need to be assigned to time slots, each job requires one such slot. Jobs can be scheduled in any order, but pairs of jobs may be in conflict in the sense that they may not be assigned to the same time slot, for example because they both rely on a shared resource. The corresponding graph contains a vertex for every job and an edge for every conflicting pair of jobs. The chromatic number of the graph is exactly the minimum make span, the optimal time to finish all jobs without conflicts. Details of the scheduling problem define the structure of the graph. For example, when assigning aircraft to flights, the resulting conflict graph is an interval graph, so the coloring problem can be solved efficiently. In bandwidth allocation to radio stations, the resulting conflict graph is a unit disk graph, so the coloring problem is 3-approximable.

4.3 Job Scheduling: Here the jobs are assumed as the vertices of the graph and there is an edge between two jobs 1 they cannot be executed simultaneously. There is a 1-1 correspondence between the feasible scheduling of the jobs and the colorings of the graph.

5. CONCLUSION

The fuzzy coloring of fuzzy graphs arises widely in modelling real life problems. Using this concept, we can represent the traffic flows whose vertices and edges both are fuzzy vertices and fuzzy arcs. Using this membership value of edges and vertices, we can introduce a method to classify the accidental zone of a traffic flows. By the interpretation of $\chi(G)$, we can show that the lower values of α are associated to lower driver aptitude levels and consequently, the traffic lights must be controlled conservatively and the chromatic number is high and for higher values of α , the driver aptitude levels increase and the chromatic number is lower, allowing a less conservative control of the traffic lights and a a lot of fluid traffic flow. And also we can use this concept in job scheduling, timetable scheduling also.

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